

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 127

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 127

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 127:0 A Song of Ascents, of Solomon.</p> <p>Psa. 127:1 Unless the LORD ^abuilds the house, They labor in vain who build it; Unless the LORD ^bguards the city, The watchman keeps awake in vain. ² It is vain for you to rise up early, To ¹retire late, To ^aeat the bread of ²painful labors; For He gives to His ^bbeloved ^ceven in his sleep.</p> <p>Psa. 127:3 Behold, ^achildren are a ¹gift of the LORD, The ^bfruit of the womb is a reward. ⁴ Like arrows in the hand of a ^awarrior, So are the children of one's youth. ⁵ How ^ablessed is the man whose quiver is full of them; ^bThey will not be ashamed When they ^cspeak with their enemies ^din the gate.</p>	<p style="text-align: right;">Psa. 127:1</p> <p style="text-align: center;">שִׁיר הַמַּעֲלוֹת לְשִׁלְמֹה</p> <p>אִם-יִבְנֶה אִם-יִבְנֶה בַּיִת שׁוּא א עֲמָלוֹ בּוֹנֵיו בּוֹ אִם-יִתֵּן לֹא- יִשְׁמְרֵ-עֵיר שׁוּא אשְׁקֵר שׁוֹמֵר : ² שׁוּא לָכֶם אִם-שָׁמַר לְיוֹם מִאֲחֵרֵי- שֵׁנָת אֲכָלִי לֶחֶם הָעֵצָבִים כִּן יִתֵּן לְיַדְיָו שֵׁנָא : ³ הַנֶּה נִחַלֵּת יִתֵּן בָּנִים שְׂכָר פְּרֵי הַבֶּטֶן : ⁴ כְּחֵצִים בְּיַד-גִּבּוֹר כִּן בְּנֵי הַנְּעוּרִים : ⁵ אֲשֶׁר־יִתְּנֵהוּ אֲשֶׁר מִלֵּא אֶת- אֲשֶׁפְתּוֹ מֵהֶם לֹא-יִבְשׁוּ כִּי-יִדְבְּרוּ אֶת-אוֹיְבֵיהֶם בַּשָּׁעַר :</p>

References

Psalm 127:1

^aPs 78:69

^bPs 121:4

Psalm 127:2

¹Lit *delay sitting*

²Lit *toils*

^aGen 3:17, 19

^bPs 60:5

Job 11:18, 19; Prov 3:24; Eccl 5:12

Psalm 127:3

¹Or *heritage*

^aGen 33:5; 48:4; Josh 24:3, 4; Ps 113:9

^bDeut 7:13; 28:4; Is 13:18

Psalm 127:4

^aPs 112:2; 120:4

Psalm 127:5

^aPs 128:2, 3

^bProv 27:11

Is 29:21; Amos 5:12

^dGen 34:20

Targum

Psa. 127:1 A song that was uttered on the ascents of the abyss, composed by Solomon. If the word of the LORD will not build the city, its builders labor in vain; if the word of the LORD is not guarding the city of Jerusalem, its guard has stayed awake in vain. ² In vain will you trouble yourselves to rise early in the morning to do robbery, who stay up late to do fornication, who eat the bread of the poor for which they labored honestly and truly; the LORD will give sleep to those who love him. [ANOTHER TARGUM: The wicked say to the righteous, “It is wrong for you that you rise early and pray in the morning and stay up late in the evening to study the Torah, eating the bread of sorrow.” The righteous reply, “Truly, the LORD gives to those who love him a complete reward for hunger.”] ³ Behold, the legacy of the LORD is proper sons, children of the womb are a reward for good deeds. ⁴ Like arrows in the hand of a warrior, so are sons of the youth. ⁵ It is good for a man that he fill his academy with them; they will not be ashamed, for they will dispute with their enemies in the gate of the place of judgment.

Spiritual Awareness

Introduction

This Psalm is a continuation of the previous one. Divine assistance is essential for a person to succeed in any endeavor. How valuable is a person's work? Work brings out the genuine glory for those who toil in it (Nedarim 49b of the Talmud). Marriage and parenthood are the noblest pursuits of a person's life but only when the LORD is a part of it. The people in Exile were reminded of marriage, parenthood and labor because it gave them a purpose.

Notes on the Psalm

It is a spiritual gift to have children if the parents will teach their children about the LORD. Without children, humanity dies out. If this happens, then everything that the LORD created was for nothing. The LORD created the Heavens and Earth so that He could create humanity and have a loving relationship with this Creation. Therefore, continuing the species is very important. Also, when teaching the ways of the LORD to one's children, the parent moves closer in their walk with the LORD. The Bible serves numerous purposes. Its Laws are there to teach us how to live a life that pleases the LORD. The Mitzvot when performed, stores spiritual gifts in Heaven for the soul. Teaching the Torah, prophets and writings to the children insures future generations will know about the love of the LORD.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

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Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

MHK V1.1 6/23/14

